

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue IV, April 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

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WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue IV (April 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Knowledge, Practices and Compliance on Subdermal Implant among Women: Basis for Proposed Information, Education, and Communication Materials

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Background of the Study

Contraceptive implants are five subdermal implants, rods the size of pencil lead, placed under the skin at the inner part of the upper arm. Implants can be used during breastfeeding without problems with milk production. The mothers' age does not affect the use of birth control implants; there is a link between the age at first birth and the use of birth control implants; the number of live-born children has a significant impact or influence on the use of implants.

The choice of becoming pregnant and the timing of women depends on biological, social, and psychological factors. With improved access to contraception, every pregnancy must be wanted and planned. However, unplanned pregnancies still occur, and the reasons are limited choice, inadequate information on contraceptive methods, and its side effects. Unintended pregnancies have a significant impact on the physical health of women and their social and psychological makeup. The burden of unplanned pregnancies is around 87 million a year (Moray et al. 2021).

Promoting family planning is essential to safeguard women's well-being while supporting community health and development. The postpartum period is the best time to counsel women about contraceptives. Subdermal implants involve the distribution of steroid progestin from polymer capsules or rods placed below the skin. It is a modern contraceptive that requires minimum compliance and has long-acting reversible fertility regulation. Their level of awareness about contraceptives is a factor that affects women in accepting subdermal implants (Torres, 2020).

Unintended pregnancies (UPs) affect the healthcare system, leading to high social costs because of maternal or fetal morbidity. Contraceptive systems are safe and effective methods allowing fertile women to prevent pregnancy, and women seeking contraception must undergo counseling on contraceptive choice. Long-acting reversible contraceptives (LARCs) (intrauterine devices (IUDs), copper (Cu)-IUD, and subdermal contraceptive implants) provide 3-year continuous pregnancy prevention and no attention needed by users. LARCs offer reversible long-term contraception and

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high continuation rates. They are strategies to prevent UPs in all women who are not aiming for a future pregnancy and those who do not want permanent contraception.

Subdermal contraceptive implants are a safe method of contraception for many women since it is easy to insert and remove and need less follow-up with the authorized facility. In addition to the birth control benefits, women's satisfaction with the method is essential and can affect their quality of life. The contraceptive implant is a reversible long-term etonogestrel-releasing device with a single rod inserted under the skin. It works by controlling fertilization by preventing the release of luteinizing hormone, a hormone that induces ovulation. It is inserted 6-8 cm above the elbow of a woman's non-dominant hand by a trained healthcare worker at the outpatient clinic. It is a progestin-only contraceptive used by any woman. It can be used for women with restrictions on estrogen-containing contraceptives. Factors contraindicated for using subdermal implants include those with liver diseases or tumors, venous thromboembolism, and pulmonary embolism (Wali et al., 2023).

The implant releases a steady low dose of progestin into the body. Progestin will prevent the ovary from releasing an egg (ovulation). It thickens the cervical mucosa, making it hard for the sperm to reach the egg. Progestin thins the uterine lining, making it difficult for a fertilized egg to implant. The implant is effective more than 99% effective in preventing conception. The birth control implant does not have many side effects. The effects slowly disappear in a few months. Potential side effects include spotting or changes in menstrual bleeding, headaches, acne, sore breasts, and mood swings (Cleveland Clinic Professional 2022).

According to Thomas (2023), the most common adverse effects of contraceptive implants are changes in the regular menstrual pattern. About 10 percent of women discontinued this method for this reason. The changes have the onset within the first three months of implant insertion and indicate the future course of bleeding for the patient. Women who submit for implants should be warned and advised to come for evaluation if abnormal bleeding develops to rule out ectopic pregnancy or any disease conditions. Changes include amenorrhea, light or irregular bleeding, frequent bleeding episodes, continuous bleeding for weeks, and occasionally menorrhagia.

Rael et al. (2020) found that the individuals had mild side effects related to their devices. Implant users reported that devices were comfortable, unintrusive, and presented minor discomfort (e.g., bruising) before or after insertion and removal. They reported removing the device because of side effects like prolonged menstruation. Participants did not mind bruising, a small scar, tenderness, or bleeding after insertion or removal.

Shaikh et al. (2021) conducted their study on mothers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the use of subdermal implants. Three hundred ninety-six adults, non-pregnant, married women of childbearing age, between 18 and 49 years, were interviewed. One hundred fifty-three respondents did not know about implants, and 122 had information from family planning clinics. Two-thirds of the respondents were in favor of using implants as a contraceptive method. Moreover, 244 respondents preferred to use Implanon, and of the 316 respondents who had ever used contraceptives, only three used implants. The respondents' favorable attitudes, limited knowledge, and poor practices were noted.

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Wali et al. 2023 made a study on the satisfaction of women using subdermal implants. 84% of the respondents were satisfied, and 19.04% were unsatisfied with the implant. The common side effects found were weight gain and menstrual irregularity. The most common cause for removal was the end of the implant's due date. Most women treated at the primary healthcare clinic were satisfied. They terminated the implant upon reaching its contraceptive duration despite manifesting side effects, and they cited to recommend it to their family and friends.

Unintended pregnancies are a significant problem in our world due to the psychological and economic distress they bring. About 45% of pregnancies were unplanned in the years 2010–2014. There is a high impact on women's health due to unsafe abortions and maternal deaths. Contraception prevents unplanned pregnancies and other consequences. Studies showed that the implant is effective, and the side effects of the implant result in higher discontinuation. The flexible implant measures four centimeters in length and two millimeters in breadth. It is inserted below the skin of a woman's upper arm by a trained healthcare provider. Once inserted sub-dermally in the arm, it can be effective for three years, and removal needs a small surgical incision (Moray et al.2021).

Mubarak et al. (2017) studied the knowledge, attitude, and utilization of implants. The majority knew one method, and one-fourth had used one, while the implant 21.9% of women used. About two-thirds were unaware of the implant, while 14.2% had good knowledge. Overall, the attitude was positive; 85% continued the method, and 14.29% stopped due to side effects. Among new users, half preferred the implant when provided with the insertion services. The knowledge about sub-dermal implants among women of reproductive age reached the optimum level. The attitude of women was positive. The factors that affect knowledge and attitude are age, parity, family type, level of education, employment status, socio-economic status, previous use of family planning, and source of information.

Jonas et al. (2021) studied the factors associated with using the birth control implant among women attending a Primary Health Clinic. Most participants who heard about the implant (9.4%) were using it, and (20.2%) intended to use it. Knowledge about the safety, beliefs in its effectiveness, easy insertion and removal, and support from intimate partners were positively associated with the intentions to use the implant in the future. It concluded limited knowledge of the implant, having completed secondary school, support from partners for women to use an implant, and the perceived expectancies of using the implant were factors associated with the use of the implant. It also ensured that contraception information is available in South African languages, regardless of educational level, comprehensive birth control education, and counseling is discussed during family planning sessions.

Matos et al. (2021) found the majority of women were willing to switch to a long-acting reversible contraceptive (LARC) when readily available to them. Considering those women who already use an implant and those who would be willing to change to it, 58% of women were underserved and not being given equal access to the subdermal implant. The inadequate availability of this type of LARC may elevate the number of unplanned pregnancies in the United States by 8% of all pregnancies per year. They

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concluded that contraceptive methods help reduce unwanted pregnancies and better serve women and their family needs.

Yimer et al. (2022) found in their study on subdermal implants that those who did not receive pre-insertion counseling, had a history of abortion, contraceptive side effects, and no appointment follow-up visit at the time of insertion were determinants of early discontinuation of the sub-dermal implant. Healthcare professionals should make an appointment for a follow-up visit at insertion and provide detailed counseling for all women.

Chapter 2 Methodology

This chapter is all about the research methodology, which includes discussions on the research design, subjects of the study, sampling scheme, data gathering instruments, statistical treatment of data, data gathering procedures, and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive research method with the questionnaire as a data gathering tool to determine women's Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance with Subdermal Implant as Contraceptive.

Population and Locale of the Study

The respondents of the study were women who had the subdermal implant as a contraceptive. The population represented by purposive sampling was used and delimited to the women registered at the Villasis Family Planning Clinic of the Rural Health Unit (RHU). The locale of the study was Villasis RHU, where women come from different barangays. It was composed of 60 mothers.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized a survey questionnaire based on previous studies and articles related to the study. Part I focused on the respondents' profiles regarding their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, number of children, and number of years using the subdermal implant. Part II tackled the knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before gathering data, the researcher secured permission from the Dean of the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies to conduct the study. When permission was granted from the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies, the researcher requested and coordinated with the Municipal Health Officer through the Public Health Nurse for permission to conduct the study in the RHU of Villasis, Pangasinan. After securing the permission, the researcher secured consent from the respondents. The researcher collected the data personally.

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Treatment of the Data

Problem Number 1 was used on the respondent's profile, frequency, and percentage. The frequency was determined based on the number of respondents who answered or checked a particular item on the questionnaire.

Chapter 3 Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the data gathered from the nurse respondents. Respondent's Profile

Table 1 shows the respondent's profile in terms of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of children, monthly family income, Religion, and number of years using subdermal implants.

Age. The majority of the respondents were in the age bracket of 21-30 years old, with a frequency of 31 or 61.7 percent; 31-40 years old, with a frequency of 17, or 28.3 percent; and 41-50, with a frequency of 12 or 30 percent. It revealed that the respondents belong to young adulthood, considered in their childbearing age.

Civil status. Most respondents were singles, with a frequency of 33 or 55 percent, followed by married, with a frequency of 27 or 45 percent. It revealed that the respondents were not yet married. It goes to show that some women had their families but were not able to undergo marriage with their partners.

Highest educational attainment. It revealed that the majority of the respondents were high school graduates, with a frequency of 33 or 55 percent, followed by those with vocational courses, with a frequency of 12 or 20 percent, elementary graduates, with a frequency of 11, or 18.3 percent, and bachelor's degree holder, with a frequency of 4, or 6.7 percent.

It showed that the majority did not pursue higher levels of learning, reaching only secondary education. It might be related to the fact that schooling entails a large budget, and most do not have the financial capability to go into tertiary education.

Number of children. It showed that most respondents had 3-4 children, with a frequency of 27 or 45 percent, 1-2 years, 24 or 40 percent, and five and above, with a frequency of 9 or 15 percent. It revealed that the respondents have an average number of children, and that is why they resort to using subdermal implants to prevent further pregnancy.

Monthly family income.

All the respondents earned an income of P10,000 and below, with a 60 or 100 percent frequency. It revealed that the respondents had a meager income for their family.

Religion. It revealed that most respondents belong to the most dominant Roman Catholic, with a frequency of 52 or 86.7 percent, Protestant and Iglesia ni Cristo, with a frequency of 4, or 6.7 percent. It revealed that the respondents belonged to the most dominant Religion in the country.

For several years, I was using a subdermal implant. The majority of the respondents used the subdermal implant for less than a year, with a frequency of 35, or

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

58.3 percent, 3-4 years, with a frequency of 14, or 23.3 percent, and 1-2 years, with a frequency of 11, or 18.3 percent. This implies that the respondents had used a subdermal implant for a few months.

Extent of Knowledge of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implant

Table 2 presents the extent of knowledge of the women on the use of subdermal implants.

The highest indicators are items 1 and 4, "subdermal implant is inserted by trained, skilled healthcare workers, and provides at least 3-year continuous pregnancy protection with a weighted mean of 4.83, and 4.63 or "Highly Knowledgeable." It revealed that the respondents were fully aware that trained health workers were the ones who inserted the implant, which was adequate for at least three years.

The lowest indicators are item numbers 7 and 8, "subdermal implant consists of polymer capsules or rods placed under the skin that ensure a slow, stable hormone delivery," and "acts by ovulation suppression, thickening of cervical mucus, and inducing endometrial atrophy," with a weighted mean of 3.15, or "Moderately Knowledgeable."

Overall, the extent of women's knowledge of the use of subdermal implants was average, with a weighted mean of 3.87, or "Knowledgeable." It revealed that the women had the information about the implant, but it was still minimal.

Extent of Practices of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants

Table 3 presents the extent of practices of the women on the use of subdermal implants.

The highest indicators are item numbers 2, 3, 5, and 10, "I strictly follow the advice about the use of subdermal implant contraceptive," "I frequently check the site of my implant to make sure it is intact," "I made sure not to have unprotected sexual contact at least seven days after the insertion of the subdermal implant," and "I am oriented by healthcare workers about the contraceptive effect, benefits, and any possible adverse events on my subdermal implant," with a weighted mean of 4.65, 4.68, and 4.63 or

"Highly Practiced." It revealed that the respondents were fully aware that trained health workers were the ones who insert the implant which is effective for at least three years and the effects and benefits of the subdermal implants.

The lowest indicators are item numbers 7, and 9, "I refer immediately when I encounter dizziness and headache," and "I will let my subdermal implant be removed when I encounter side effects like nausea, stomach cramping, and weight gain," with a weighted mean of 3.20, and 3.47 or "Moderately Practiced."

Overall, the extent of practices of women on the use of subdermal implants got an average weighted mean of 4.12, or "Practiced." It implies that the women did different practices on the use of subdermal implants however, they should continuously seek the advice of health professionals for effective use.

Extent of Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants

Table 4 presents the extent of compliance of the women on the use of subdermal implants.

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The highest indicator is item numbers 2, 3, 4, 8, and 9, "I followed the no sex for one week after the insertion of subdermal implant," "I refrain from wetting the insertion site for three days after the insertion," "I clean the site every day with betadine solution and apply band-aid for three days," "I submitted for reinsertion of new PSI before the three year expiry period," and "I stopped placing the elastic bandage after three days of insertion," with a weighted mean of 4.63, 4.72, and 4.57 or "Highly Compliant." It revealed that the respondents complied with the basic practices on the use of subdermal implants.

The lowest indicators are items numbers 1, and 6, "I submit for regular check-up in the health center," and "I took pain reliever when I felt pain at the site of insertion," with a weighted mean of 3.63, and 3.58 or

"Compliant."

Overall, the extent of practices of women on the use of subdermal implants got an average weighted mean of 4.35, or "Compliant." It implies that when the women are compliant, then it goes to show that they are willing to use the subdermal implant.

Extent of Knowledge, Practices and Compliance of Women

on the Use of Subdermal Implants

Table 5 presents the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants.

Among the three indicators, the highest fall on the "Compliance" of women on the use of subdermal implants, with a weighted mean of 4.35, followed by "Practices" with a weighted mean of 4.12, and the lowest on "Knowledge," with a weighted mean of 3.87. Therefore, women must increase their knowledge of its use. Overall, the women using the subdermal implant were more compliant as compared to practices and knowledge.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants across Age

Table 6 images the difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across ages. Data reveal that age has no significant effect on the extent of practices and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants, as shown in the computed F-values of .709 and 2.610, respectively. On the other hand, age has a significant effect on the extent of knowledge of women on the use of subdermal implants, with an F-value of 3.761 and a significance value of .029. It revealed that those with higher age were more knowledgeable compared to those younger ones. It might also be related that they had more knowledge since they were much older than the other women.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Knowledge of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants across Age

Table 7 presents the results of the Scheffe test on the significant difference in the extent of knowledge of women on the use of subdermal implants across ages.

Statistical data reveal that women under the age bracket 21-30 have significantly different extent of knowledge on the use of subdermal implants as compared to women aged 41-50.

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This is also true for women under the age brackets 31-40 compared to women with age 41-50.

The negative mean difference between the compared groups indicates that women who belong to the older age bracket have a significantly higher extent of knowledge on the use of subdermal implants as compared to the younger age groups.

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants across Civil Status

Table 8 displays the t-test results on the difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across civil status.

The computed t-values along these 3 aspects have generated significance values which are all higher than the set .05 level of significance. This suggests acceptance of the null hypothesis. Hence, the difference is no significant in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants when grouped according to civil status. Being single or married does not affect the extent of knowledge, practice, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants. It implies that regardless of their civil status does not affect their knowledge, practices, and compliance with contraceptives.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants across Highest Educational Attainment

Table 9 presents the difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across the highest educational attainment.

Significant results are revealed with the computed F-values generating significance values, which are all lower than the set .05 level of significance. Data indicate that the highest educational attainment of women causes differences in their extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance with the use of subdermal implants. This finding is similar to the study by Jonas et al. (2021) that there was limited knowledge of the implant, having completed secondary school, support from partners for women to use implants, and the perceived expectancies of using the implant were factors associated with the use of the implant.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use

of Subdermal Implants across the Highest Educational Attainment

Table 10 discloses the groups that have shown significant differences in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across the highest educational attainment.

Data on the table display significant negative mean differences between the compared groups.

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This means that the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women with higher educational attainment are significantly higher than those who finished a lower level of education. It implies that those more educated women had a higher extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance on the use of subdermal implants.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants across the Number of Children

Table 11 presents the difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across several children. The computed F-value of .986 with a significance value of .379 implies that the difference in the extent of knowledge of women on the use of subdermal implants when the number of children is taken into consideration has no significant.

Conversely, the number of children was found to affect the extent of practices and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants. The results of the Scheffe test are shown in the next table. It reflects that having several children does not affect their knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on contraceptive use.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Practices and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants Across Number of Children

Table 12 shows the significant difference in the extent of practices and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across several children.

The significant positive mean difference in the indicated groups implies that the women with less number of children have a significantly higher extent of practice and compliance with the use of subdermal implants as compared to the group of women with a greater number of children. It reflects that those with less number of children were more compliant and a higher extent of practice may be due to having more time to know more about the subdermal implant.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants across Religion

Table 13 reveals the difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across religions. The computed F-values under knowledge and practices have generated significance values that are higher than the set .05 level of significance.

Therefore, the null hypothesis must be accepted. There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge and practices of women on the use of subdermal implants.

On the other hand, a significant difference exists in the extent of compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants. This means that Religion affects the compliance of these women with the use of subdermal implants. It reflects that their Religion somewhat affects how they comply with the use of contraceptives.

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Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Extent of Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants across Religion

Table 14 displays the significant difference in the extent of compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across religions.

The negative mean differences indicate that the women who belong to the Iglesia ni Cristo and Protestant denominations have claimed to have a higher extent of compliance with the use of subdermal implants than those who are affiliated with the Roman Catholic faith. It implies that those in other religions Iglesia ni Cristo and Protestants had their reasons for having higher compliance on subdermal implant use.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants

across several Years Using Subdermal Implant

Table 15 displays the difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across several years using subdermal implants.

The computed F-values which are all lower than the set .05 level of significance, it repudiate the null hypothesis. There is a significant difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants when their number of years of using subdermal implants is considered.

It reflects that those who had been using the implant for longer years had a higher extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance on contraceptive use.

Table 16 provides the results of the Scheffe Test on the significant difference in the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants across several years using subdermal implant.

The negative mean differences in knowledge indicate that women who have been using subdermal implants for a longer time have a significantly higher extent of knowledge.

Meanwhile, the significant positive mean differences in practices and compliance imply that women who have been using subdermal implants for a shorter period have a significantly higher extent of practice and compliance than those who have been using it for a longer time.

Relationship Between the Extent of Knowledge, Practices, and Compliance of Women on the Use of Subdermal Implants and their Profile Variables

Table 17 displays the relationship between the extent of knowledge, practices, and compliance of women on the use of subdermal implants and their profile variables.

As to the extent of knowledge, significant positive R-values are shown under age, highest educational attainment, and number of years of using subdermal implant. This indicates that the older the women, and have attained a higher educational level with a greater number of years of using subdermal implants, the higher the extent of their knowledge on the use of subdermal implants.

When it comes to the extent of practices, a significant positive R-value is revealed under the highest educational attainment. Hence, higher educational attainment of women indicates a higher extent of practice on the use of subdermal implants.

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However, significant negative R-values are shown under several children and several years of using subdermal implants. Results suggest that less number of children with a lower number of years of using subdermal implants indicate a higher extent of practice on the use of subdermal implants.

Finally, as to compliance, significant positive R-values are shown under highest educational attainment and Religion. This means that as women earn a higher level of education with divergence from the Roman Catholic faith, the higher their compliance with the use of subdermal implants.

On the other hand, significant negative R-values are indicated under age, number of children, and number of years of using subdermal implants. This implies that younger women, with less number of children and less number of years of using subdermal implants, have a higher extent of compliance with the use of subdermal implants.

Chapter 4

Recommendations and Conclusion

This chapter presented the recommendations and the conclusions based on the findings of the study. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following are hereby concluded.

The respondents were young adults, with no marital relationship, did not pursue a higher level of education, with an average number of children, earning below the poverty level, belonging to the most dominant Religion, and using the subdermal implant for a few months.

The respondents were more compliant with the use of subdermal implants, followed by their practices, and lowest on their knowledge.

Women under the age bracket 21-30, higher educational attainment, those with less number of children, that Religion, and those using subdermal implants for shorter periods have significantly different extents of knowledge, practices, and compliance on the use of subdermal implants.

The older the women, and have attained a higher educational level with a greater number of years of using subdermal implants, the higher the extent of their knowledge on the use of subdermal implants, while women, with less number of children and less number of years of using subdermal implants, have higher extent of compliance on the use of subdermal implants.

The proposed Information, Education, and communication material is prepared for distribution to women who visit the health center for consultation.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions provided, the following are hereby offered:

The respondents must enrich their knowledge about subdermal implants for them to fully understand and thereby be effective in preventing pregnancy.

The women must raise their knowledge and practices on the use of the contraceptive implant by attending regularly the orientations or seminars conducted by the healthcare providers.

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WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue IV (April 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The women must increase their knowledge, practices, and compliance on the contraceptive implant to attain the objective and real purpose of using the implant

Regardless of their profile variables, the women must intensify to understand the facts regarding subdermal implants for effective use.

The proposed IEC materials can be of help to women seeking birth spacing or pregnancy prevention.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11000783

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